

Isolation of Bound Ascorbic Acid (Ascorbigen) from Cabbage

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Bound ascorbic acid (ascorbigen) has been isolated from cabbage juice by adsorption on active charcoal and purification by chromatography on silica gel column with gradient elution. Ascorbigen shows reactions for ascorbic acid and an indole moiety.

It has already been reported that a certain amount of ascorbic acid is present in a bound form, called 'ascorbigen', in cabbage, cauliflower, and some other plant materials and that the substance can be extracted from cabbage (Guha *et al.*, *Nature*, 1936, 137, 946; 1938, 141, 974; Pal and Guha, this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 481). Sengupta and Guha (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 496) and Ghosh and Guha (*ibid.*, 1939, 16, 505) concentrated ascorbigen from cabbage to a considerable extent, but the substance was still gummy and obviously impure.

Recently Sumcov (*Biochimija*, 1950, 15, 112), Terent'eva (*ibid.*, 1953, 18, 296), and Procházka (*Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 1643) took up this problem and Procházka *et al.* (*Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1957, 22, 654) claimed the isolation of ascorbigen from cabbage juice in a pure state and postulated a structure consisting of ascorbic acid and an indole moiety. The problem of isolation of ascorbigen was taken up in this laboratory again in 1956 and a preliminary communication was published elsewhere (Malakar and Guha, *Science & Culture*, 1958, 24, 147).

The present communication deals with the method used in this laboratory for the isolation of what appears to be pure ascorbigen from cabbage. The preparation obtained is free from ascorbic acid as it does not reduce 2, 6-dichlorophenol indophenol. On hydrolysis, however, it releases ascorbic acid which has been identified both chromatographically and by the formation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of dehydroascorbic acid derived from it. The substance shows reactions for indole. It closely resembles the substance obtained by Procházka *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) in appearance, composition, and properties and is probably identical with it.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cabbage (37 kg.), purchased from the local market, was washed and allowed to drain. It was cut into small pieces by a sharp stainless steel knife, repeatedly passed through a meat mincer, and the juice expressed by a screw press. The residue was mixed with about 8 litres of water, passed through the meat mincer twice, and pressed. The pressed juices were mixed (about 30 litres) and centrifuged in a Sharples supercentrifuge. The juice (pH 6.2) after centrifugation was taken in four aluminium buckets and active charcoal (25 g.) (E. Merck) was added in each bucket. After 4 hours' occasional stirring the liquid was

centrifuged and the charcoal pressed. The charcoal adsorbed about 70% of the bound ascorbic acid from the juice.

Various solvents, e.g., chloroform, ethyl acetate, 95% ethanol, 50% ethanol, and mixtures of chloroform and 95% ethanol (7:3 v/v and 3:7 v/v) were tried for elution of ascorbigen from charcoal. A mixture of chloroform and 95% ethanol (7:3, v/v) was found to be the best elutrient among these.

The charcoal was refluxed twice at 80° for one hour with a mixture of chloroform and 95% ethanol (7:3, v/v). About 35% ascorbigen was eluted by first extraction and another 15% by second extraction, totalling about 50%. A negligible amount was eluted by the third extraction. The extracts were mixed and concentrated by distillation under reduced pressure at 40° to a dark sticky mass. While cabbage juice contained about 0.5 mg. ascorbigen in terms of ascorbic acid per g. of total solid, this concentrate contained about 15-25 mg. ascorbigen per g. of total solid. The yield was about 28% of ascorbigen present in cabbage. The concentration effected was thus about 30 to 50 times. The concentrate (vacuum-dried) is soluble in water, ethanol, methanol, butanolⁿ, acetone, and ethyl acetate; it is less soluble in chloroform and practically insoluble in benzene and petroleum ether.

The vacuum-dried concentrate was dissolved in acetone, filtered, and added to an equal volume of petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). A dark red, oily liquid separated and this contained the major portion (about 95%) of ascorbigen. This oily substance had a specific activity* of about 50 mg./g. total solid and contained about 25% of ascorbigen present in cabbage.

Attempts were made to further purify this red liquid. It was dried in vacuum and chromatographic separation was attempted on cellulose (Schleicher and Schüll, Nr 123) column (1 cm x 15 cm; 3g.). The following solvents were tried as irrigating liquids: water-saturated ethyl acetate, water-saturated butylⁿ acetate, water-saturated butanolⁿ, water-saturated phenol, butanolⁿ: acetic acid: water (4:1:5, v/v), butanolⁿ: petroleum ether (4:6, v/v). Of these, water-saturated butylⁿ acetate seemed to be the best, giving a fraction having a specific activity of 100 mg./g. total solid. This fraction contained about 15% of ascorbigen present in cabbage. On rechromatography, specific activity up to 130 mg./g. total solid could be obtained, but there was a loss of about 50% in yield. No further purification could be obtained on cellulose column.

As the partitioning power of cellulose for ascorbigen and impurities seemed to be low, attempts were made to fractionate the material on a silica gel (E. Merck, 0.2-0.5 mm for column chromatography) column (17 cm x 1.2 cm; 15g.). By using ethyl acetate and chloroform in the ratio of 1:1 (v/v) as the irrigating liquid, a fraction was obtained having a specific activity of 230 mg./g. total solid. Only 6.8 mg. out of 16 mg. (sp. activity 50 mg./g.) taken for chromatography was present in this fraction. This fraction containing about 10% of ascorbigen present in cabbage was rechromatographed and one fraction probably contained pure ascorbigen, as its specific activity (about 500 mg./g.) did not change on further chromatography. But the yield was very poor (only 0.4 mg. out of 6.8 mg.). This fraction contained only about 0.6% of ascorbigen present in cabbage. As the procedure was very time-consuming and required a large volume of irrigating liquid, stage chromatography was abandoned in favour of chromatography with gradient elution. To facilitate the rate

*Specific activity—mg. of ascorbigen (in terms of ascorbic acid) per g. of total solid.

of progress, an apparatus was made containing five silica gel columns with one reservoir and one mixing vessel (Fig. 1).

In this method ethyl acetate was kept in a separating funnel (500 c.c.) at a high level and with the help of adjustable narrow glass tubes it was allowed to fall dropwise into a lower vessel (1 litre) containing chloroform. This vessel was provided with side tubes (with stop cocks) to which were fitted the silica gel columns (14 cm $\times$ 1.5 cm; 15 g.). Into each column, about 0.25 g. of ascorbigen (sp. activity 50 mg./g.) was introduced. All the connections were of ground-glass fittings. The contents of the vessel were stirred continuously with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The apparatus was so regulated that the rate of outflow from the silica gel columns was equal to that of inflow into the vessel from the separating funnel above. Fractions (25 c.c.) were collected at intervals of about 30 minutes.

The active substance began to appear in the 7th fraction and was present in maximum amount in the 9th fraction. The concentration then began to decrease gradually and the substance practically disappeared in the 12th fraction. The fraction having the highest amount contained 30% of the original amount taken for chromatography and the specific activity was about 230 mg./g. total solid. This fraction containing about 8% of ascorbigen present in cabbage was rechromatographed and this yielded a product which on further chromatography did not increase in specific activity (about 500 mg./g.). Yield was about one tenth of the amount originally taken for chromatography and contained about 2.5% of ascorbigen present in cabbage.

Properties of Ascorbigen.—Ascorbigen is a faintly yellowish powder, m.p. 84°. It is amorphous. Attempts to crystallise it were unsuccessful. It is highly hygroscopic and photosensitive, becoming brown to reddish on exposure to light. It is labile to acid and alkali. It shows reaction for indole with Ehrlich's reagent. It does not respond to the test for ascorbic acid unless hydrolysed with acid. It is dialysable.

Chromatographic Identification of Ascorbic Acid as a Moiety of Ascorbigen

Indophenol-reducing substance could not be detected in ascorbigen unless it was hydrolysed with acid. Spots of (a) ascorbigen, (b) hydrolysed ascorbigen, (c) pure ascorbic acid, and (d) hydrolysed ascorbigen plus pure ascorbic acid were given on Whatman paper No. 1. By ascending chromatography in a solvent mixture of butanol²: acetic acid; water (4:1:5) with a drop of 10% KCN (to keep ascorbic acid in reduced condition), spots with the same R_f (0.48) were detected on spraying with 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol in all cases except in that of ascorbigen. Spots with the same R_f (0.75) were also detected

FIG. 1

on spraying with the indophenol dye on Whatman paper No. 1 using a solvent mixture of methanol : butanol^a (4 : 1, v/v) in all cases except in that of ascorbigen. This shows that ascorbigen on hydrolysis produces ascorbic acid which can be identified chromatographically.

Further Identification of Ascorbic Acid formed from Ascorbigen

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative of dehydroascorbic acid, formed from ascorbic acid released by hydrolysis of ascorbigen, was prepared. Ascorbigen was dissolved in 5% metaphosphoric acid, heated on a boiling water bath in CO₂ atmosphere for 30 minutes; cooled, and filtered. Saturated bromine water was added to the filtrate in excess. Thiourea (2%) in 50% ethanol was added till the colour disappeared; 1 c.c. was added in excess. 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine (50 c.c.) in 9*N*-H₂SO₄ was added to this solution and incubated at 37° for 6 days. The precipitated hydrazone derivative was filtered, washed with water, dissolved in methanol, and reprecipitated by the addition of water. The process was repeated several times. The precipitate was dissolved in 50% ice-cold H₂SO₄ and precipitated by careful addition of water. It was filtered, washed with water, and dissolved in absolute acetone. The volume was reduced by warming, cooled, and the hydrazone derivative allowed to crystallise; m.p. 272°. The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative from pure ascorbic acid was similarly prepared and purified; m.p. 271° (mixed m.p. 272°). This provides further evidence that ascorbigen contains ascorbic acid in a bound form.

Composition.—The elemental composition of ascorbigen is C, 58.78; H, 4.66; N, 3.72%. Procházka and Šanda (*Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1960, 25, 276) have given the elemental composition of their product as C, 58.74; H, 5.64; N, 4.36%.

Absorption spectra.—The absorption maxima and minima (with extinction coefficients) of ascorbigen are: $\lambda_{\max}$ 220 m μ (ϵ 4.52), 273 m μ (ϵ 3.77), 280 m μ (ϵ 3.79), 290 m μ (ϵ 3.73); $\lambda_{\min}$ 256 m μ (ϵ 3.59), 276 m μ (ϵ 3.77), 287 m μ (ϵ 3.69), whereas the corresponding data of Procházka's substance are: $\lambda_{\max}$ 220 m μ (ϵ 4.52), 273 m μ (ϵ 3.77), 280 m μ (ϵ 3.80), 290 m μ (ϵ 3.71); $\lambda_{\min}$ 245 m μ (ϵ 3.30), 276 m μ (ϵ 3.75), 287 m μ (ϵ 3.66).

Electrophoretic Studies.—Paper ionopheresis in phosphate buffer solution at pH 6.0 and 4.4 (ionic strength 0.05, voltage 220, milliamp 11, time 16 hours, temperature 4° ± 1°) indicates that ascorbigen is electroneutral at these hydrogen-ion concentrations.

Attempts to prepare some derivatives of the substance have so far been unsuccessful owing to the very small amount of material available and its great lability to acid and alkali.

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